

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AL-QUAID****FIRST NAME: NASREEN****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office Word on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. The Importance of Academic Writing (Nixon 2018)
2. Types of Academic Writing (University of Sydney, n.d.)
3. The Steps of Academic Writing (EUCLID 2021, 8-10; Linnaeus University, n.d.)
4. The Structure of an Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-12; Linnaeus University, n.d.)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
6. The Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-57)

THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

When contemplating the subject of academic writing, one can recall a familiar scene whereby an aspiring researcher stands before a full auditorium of fellow scientists, presenting his work and findings to the consortium. The research and theories are consolidated into an academic essay with the necessary evidence and references. Why is this required and important to academic work?

Academic essays and writing have been used for centuries to support academic work in various fields, from science and medicine to politics and history. It provides the backbone by which ideas can be proposed through the careful and deliberate presentation of the proposals to support academic work. According to the ACA-401 course pack for period one, “Academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 7).

To understand academic writing more, we need to delve into the importance of academic writing as a whole and the types of academic writing that exist. Following this,

we must understand the actual steps of academic writing, the structure of the essay and how to complete a piece with plagiarism, editing conventions and references in mind.

2) IMPORTANCE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Many aspects to academic writing make it an important skill to learn and master. Academic essay writing not only encourages professionalism in writing but also teaches elements of structure and technique. Researching topics and establishing a methodology to analyze information is valuable in any academic setting. The writing cooperative indicates that this “education will help you to think critically and form an opinion” (Nixon 2018). It is these opinions that may go on to formulate new ideas in various fields of study. In this way, academic writing can be a pathway to the creation of new methods and the adoption of new ideas and is, therefore, a valuable tool to learn and develop.

3) TYPES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Although there are many different types of essays, the realm of academic writing using formal, objective (impersonal), or technical language generally has four main types: descriptive, analytical, persuasive, and critical writing (University of Sydney n.d.). Descriptive writing can provide facts in the form of a report, record, or summary of technical information. It is simple and is the kind of writing that provides facts. On the other hand, analytical writing seeks to analyze these facts and compare, contrast, or examine their significance. This kind of analysis can draw parallels between data and can be used to support theories or academic findings. Persuasive writing in an academic essay may include arguing for or against a certain point of view. It could be used to develop an argument, recommend, or take a position based on research findings. Finally, critical writing, just as its name implies, requires one to critique or debate an issue. This could entail providing evidence for a certain point of view and analyzing alternate interpretations.

4) STEPS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Varying sources will indicate that there are between eight to ten steps of good academic essay writing. These smaller steps are generally blocked into three main stages; pre-writing, drafting, and final revising, including editing and proofreading (Linnaeus University, n.d.) The pre-writing stage generally consists of choosing a topic and brainstorming ideas for your essay. It can also include establishing points of view, researching the topic using credible sources, and taking notes, as specified in Figure 1. Basic Steps of Writing an Essay (EUCLID 2021, 8). The research will help to narrow down a thesis and develop an essay plan.

The drafting stage can begin once ideas are organized, and a plan has been established. Next, the plan can be used to make an initial outline, and then a preliminary draft of the academic essay can be written. The draft essay should consist of an

introduction, body, and conclusion and should serve the purpose of getting ideas down on paper. The essay does not need to be perfect at this stage, and “letting your thinking and writing flow as freely as possible” (Linnaeus University, n.d.) can ensure that original ideas and unique perspectives come through.

The final main writing stage is the revising stage which can be done one to two days after the initial draft. The revising stage generally includes proofreading, editing, and redrafting if need be. This stage aims to ensure that the test is “coherent and written accurately” (Linnaeus University, n.d.) This can include the consistency and clarity of the writing as well as grammar, spelling, and punctuation. Once this stage is complete, an academic essay can be given to a colleague to critique and revise further if need be. Finally, once all references have been checked and listed at the end of the paper, the completed essay can be handed in.

5) STRUCTURE OF AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

Now that the steps of writing are identified, the structure of the essay must also be considered. The basic structure of any essay includes an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. An academic essay, however, may include additional structure, including sub-headings, conjunctions, and sentences that refer to the main idea and reflect a clear thesis or stance on an issue. A good essay will include this clear structure, appropriate references, academic language, and an analytical, persuasive, or critical focus (University of Sydney, n.d.).

The analysis that is included in an academic essay may be divided into paragraphs, and “each paragraph in the body of the essay should deal with one main point/ aspect” (EUCLID, 2021, 11) of the argument. Therefore, the topic sentence may introduce the point of that particular paragraph and follow with supporting sentences and evidence from a reference source or examples. The paragraph should also contain your analysis or significance for including it in the essay and a “critical conclusion that can be drawn from the evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 11).

The body of the academic will thereby contain several paragraphs that can explain the stance of your essay and overall analysis in a clear and structured format. The points within your paragraphs must also be referenced appropriately to enhance the argument's credibility and avoid plagiarism. These references should be listed on the last page of an academic essay. A successful academic essay will have all of these aspects and will be sufficiently edited, corrected, and accomplish the assignment's goal by relaying a clear answer, stance, or analysis of the issue before it can be completed.

6) PLAGIARISM

Following a specific set of steps and structure for an academic essay can ensure that the information that has been collected and organized is presented authentically. According to the ACA-401 course pack, some examples of plagiarism include “having someone write

a paper for you or taking someone else’s words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting” (EUCLID 2021, 34). Once this is understood, plagiarism can be avoided by giving credit to authors and citing sources for the information collected. The main takeaway that may not be understood is that using ideas in academic writing is permitted as long as the source is cited. The writer of the essay develops the subsequent analysis of the point. The course pack details many tips and examples of paraphrasing and citing, which detail when ideas or text needs to be cited.

7) THE CHICAGO STYLE

A final point to consider when completing an academic essay is the style and formatting of the finished piece. Academic institutions or organizations may impose a style on the text or want to adhere to a format from a certain industry. Chicago style, sometimes referred to as “Turabian” style, is a manner of formatting that is commonly used for books and research papers. The ACA-401D course pack introduces this style for academic essays and details manners of abbreviation, capitalization, and endnotes. Utilizing a specific format adds an element of structure and can help establish consistency in future academic essays.

8) CONCLUSION

The importance of understanding the actual steps of academic writing, the structure of the essay, and how to complete a piece with plagiarism, editing conventions, and references in mind cannot be underestimated when embarking on a field of study. The process of developing an idea, researching, and formulating a thesis is a process that enables academia to move forward and set new precedents for learning. It is an invaluable tool that students of any group or discipline can master and utilize to create a meaningful impact in the field or audience they wish to influence.

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